

Association of Subclinical Hypothyroidism with Bad Obstetric History: A Review

Dr. Raima Nasir

SPR at Women and Children MTI Bannu. docraima23@gmail.com

Dr. Uzlifat Khattak*

MBBS, FCPS (Gynaecology & Obstetrics), Women Medical Officer (WMO) THQ Hospital BD Shah District Karak. Corresponding Author Email: arshiakhan823@gmail.com

Dr. Tanzila Aftab

Assistant Professor, Gynae and OBS, HITEC IMS, Taxila / HIT Hospital, Taxila. drtanzila.aftab@gmail.com

Author Details

Keywords:	
Bad obstetric history, Levothyroxine, Pregnancy complications, Subclinical hypothyroidism, Thyroid peroxidase antibodies	
Received on 14 Aug 2025	
Accepted on 15 Sept 2025	
Published on 18 Sept 2025	
Corresponding Authors*:	E-mails &
Dr. Uzlifat Khattak	
arshiakhan823@gmail.com	

Abstract

Objectives: To review the association between subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) and bad obstetric history (BOH), focusing on prevalence, outcomes, and management. **Study Design and Setting:** Narrative review of published studies on SCH in women with BOH, retrieved from major medical databases. **Methodology:** Relevant literature was searched using keywords related to SCH, pregnancy, and obstetric outcomes. Data were synthesized on epidemiology, diagnostic criteria, risk factors, pregnancy outcomes, and treatment. **Results:** SCH affects 2–19% of pregnancies, with prevalence influenced by iodine intake, population, and diagnostic thresholds. SCH is linked to recurrent miscarriage, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, intrauterine growth restriction, stillbirth, and low birth weight. The risk is higher

among thyroid peroxidase antibody-positive women. Evidence suggests levothyroxine therapy reduces miscarriage and neonatal complications, though its effect on broader maternal outcomes remains debated. Despite growing evidence, universal screening and treatment for SCH are not consistently practiced, especially in resource-limited settings.

Conclusions: SCH is a significant but underdiagnosed contributor to adverse obstetric outcomes, particularly in women with BOH. Early detection and appropriate management with levothyroxine may improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

Standardized screening guidelines and further large-scale studies are needed to integrate SCH management into routine obstetric care.

INTRODUCTION

Amongst the endocrine diseases seen during pregnancy, thyroid diseases are second most common endocrine disorder. After conception, thyroid hormone maintains the reproductive hormonal status and also responsible for growth and neurodevelopment of fetus. Pregnancy significantly affects thyroid gland functioning, increasing the demand for thyroid hormone (1). Excess or deficiency of thyroid hormone interferes with ovulation and fertility, and if the woman gets pregnant, it affects fetomaternal outcomes (2).

The prevalence of overt hypothyroidism during pregnancy is 0.5% and that of subclinical hypothyroidism is 2-3%. Subclinical hypothyroidism is defined as serum TSH > 4.5 mIU/L with normal FT4. There is strong association of subclinical hypothyroidism with miscarriage, preterm birth, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, still birth and anemia (3). There is increased risk of pregnancy complications in women with subclinical hypothyroidism and the risk is more increased if the woman is thyroid peroxidase antibody positive (4) (5).

Bad obstetric history is defined as women having history of recurrent miscarriages, stillbirth, intrauterine growth restriction, early neonatal deaths, preeclampsia and gestational diabetes (1).

Numerous studies have found inconsistent associations between subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy and adverse obstetrical outcomes. However Meiqin Wu et al reported high frequency of subclinical hypothyroidism is associated with bad obstetric outcome. There is lack of awareness about screening of patients with bad obstetric

history for subclinical hypothyroidism and no recommendations are available for treatment of such patients. In most of our hospitals, neither screening is done nor is treatment with thyroxin offered (7).

Existing literature support the relationship of subclinical hypothyroidism with bad obstetric history and its treatment with levothyroxine, which is still not the part of clinical practice. Further research and recommendations are needed in this field to guide clinical practice.

This review article will provide a comprehensive understanding of the association; guiding future research directions and potential interventions to optimize maternal and fetal outcome in patient with bad obstetric history due to subclinical hypothyroidism.

BODY OF REVIEW ARTICLE

SOURCES AND SELECTION CRITERIA

References are identified through searches of publications listed by PubMed, Embase, Web of Science and Scopus, Semantic scholar. Keywords are used to search for studies of subclinical hypothyroidism in women planning conception and during pregnancy.

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF HYPOTHYROIDISM AND SUBCLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM IN PREGNANCY

Accurate determination of incidence of subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy is complicated due to differences in diagnostic criteria used over the time. American Thyroid Association guidelines of 2011 labeled subclinical hypothyroidism at serum TSH ≥ 2.5 mIU/L in first trimester(1). Song W used these criteria and reported the incidence of subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy 2-3 % (3). According to American thyroid association guidelines of 2017, Subclinical hypothyroidism is defined as serum TSH ≥ 4.5 mIU/L with normal FT4, the incidence of SCH according to the 2017 ATA standard

was only 1.93%, in a study conducted in China(4).Prospective and Retrospective observational data from individual large cohorts in various countries presented incidence for subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy ranging between 2-19%(Table 1)(2)(7)(9)(10)(11) (12).

Sohail et al conducted a cross-sectional multi-center study, over a period of 12 months. Pregnant females in the first trimester of pregnancy were recruited from the antenatal clinics of seven centers from six Pakistani cities. They assessed the frequency of SCH in pregnant females and associated risk factors. A total of 500 pregnant women were enrolled in this study. Only 1.6% of women had a newly-diagnosed SCH. While 1.2% of women had hyperthyroidism, 6% had known hypothyroidism, and 1% had overt hypothyroidism (39).

Most of the studies conducted to determine the prevalence and consequences of hypothyroidism during pregnancy, are done on Western populations. Thyroid function is dependent on nutritional iodine intake, environmental factors, diet, body habitus, and genetic predisposition, which can vary among different populations. So it is necessary to estimate the prevalence and adverse effects of thyroid dysfunction on pregnancy in different populations (37)

TABLE1. INDIVIDUAL ESTIMATES OF THE INCIDENCE OF SUBCLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM FROM STUDIES OF VARIOUS COUNTRIES

Ref	Country, year	No. of Pregnancies	Prevalence of SCH (%)
9	Spain, 2012-2018	17281	6.45%
2	Pakistan	9526	4.58%

	2019-2020		
7	China	7587	2.68%
	2015		
10	Turkey	796	8.9%
	2014-2015		
11	Nepal	329	19.7%
	2020		
12	India	200	7%
	2017-2018		
27	Tehran	500	12%
40	Saudi Arabia	384	13%
	Jan-Aug 2016		

CAUSES OF SCH

Two most common causes of SCH are

1. Iodine deficiency (developing countries)
2. Autoimmune hypothyroidism (developed countries)
3. Radioiodine therapy
4. Surgery for hypothyroidism (28).

So all women planning pregnancy, pregnant women, and breast feeding should receive daily iodine supplementation of 250ug daily(13)(21).

In developed countries, main cause of hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis .Thyroid autoantibodies are detected in 50% of women with subclinical hypothyroidism and 10% of biochemically euthyroid women (14). The 2017ATA

guidelines recommend that all pregnant women with TSH concentrations >2.5 mIU/L should be evaluated for TPOAB status(15)(2).

SCREENING OF SUBCLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM

Considering the risk associated with subclinical hypothyroidism, some studies suggest that in places where technical and financial support is available, TSH testing should be performed in all pregnant women as early as possible, ideally at the beginning of first trimester or even in preconception planning (23). In places with less access to laboratory test, screening is reserved for cases, in which risk factors of hypothyroidism are present like, symptoms and signs of thyroid dysfunction, type 1 diabetes mellitus, goiter, other autoimmune diseases and TPOAB positivity(16)(17). Symptoms and signs during early pregnancy will not help in detection of women at risk of thyroid hypo function, as physiological symptoms of early pregnancy overlap with symptoms of hypothyroidism (18)

According to 2017 ATA guidelines there is no need to do screening of all women during preconception or pregnancy, except women planning assisted reproduction and women who are thyroid peroxidase antibody positive(5). Positivity for antibodies against thyroid peroxidase (TPOAb) is common in women of childbearing age with an incidence rate of 1–2.4%. TPOAb-positivity may alter the fertilization and implantation processes or cause early missed abortions. Women positive for TPOAb are at a significant risk of developing hypothyroidism during pregnancy and postpartum so screening for thyroid disorders in pregnancy should include assessment of both TSH and TPOAb (19). Progression from subclinical to overt hypothyroidism occurs in 3–20% of women with thyroid autoimmunity (20).

COMPARISON OF SUBCLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM WITH OVERT HYPOTHYROIDISM IN THE CONTEXT OF PREGNANCY

Untreated or uncontrolled overt hypothyroidism during pregnancy increase the incidence of maternal anemia, preeclampsia, spontaneous abortion, low birth weight (LBW), fetal death, or stillbirth (37) (48). Whether these complications occur in women with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) during pregnancy remains controversial (22) (47). A more recent study conducted by Jain et al says that overt and subclinical hypothyroidism, both has similar adverse effects on maternal and fetal outcomes (20) (23) (24) (25).

Another study conducted in Nepal showed higher incidence of poor maternal and fetal outcome in overt hypothyroid group as compared to subclinical hypothyroid group (26) (43).

A study was conducted in Bangladesh to compare the fetomaternal outcome in overt and subclinical hypothyroidism. They found that 86% patient of subclinical hypothyroidism conceived within 2 years and 67% of patients of overt hypothyroidism conceived within 5 years. The incidence of recurrent miscarriage was significantly higher in overt hypothyroidism group. The incidence of pregnancy induced hypertension (43%), intrauterine growth restriction ($P=0.001$), gestational diabetes (38%) as compared to subclinical hypothyroidism. Neonatal complications were significantly more in overt hypothyroidism group. Mean TSH level was significantly ($p<0.05$) higher in overt hypothyroidism patients but mean FT4 level was almost similar in both groups. In this analysis results showed that overt hypothyroidism among Bangladeshi pregnant women are associated with more maternal complication & adverse parental outcome than subclinical hypothyroidism. The adequate treatment of hypothyroidism during

gestation minimizes risks and generally, makes it possible for pregnancies to be carried to term without complications. Significant adverse effects on maternal and fetal outcome were seen emphasizing the importance of routine antenatal thyroid screening (43).

A study conducted in India by Kumari et al, common complication observed in subclinical hypothyroidism was preeclampsia (9.56%) followed by preterm delivery (7.82%) and abortions. However, in overt hypothyroidism the incidence of preeclampsia, preterm delivery and abortions was 20%, 10% and 5% respectively. Major fetal complications in hypothyroid mothers (subclinical as well as overt) were intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), low birth weight and stillbirth (44).

A study conducted by Joshi et al, in Bikaner, Rajasthan, India showed incidence of hemorrhage in early pregnancy, miscarriage, preterm labour is higher in subclinical hypothyroidism as compared to overt hypothyroidism(45).

A study conducted by Gupta et al, showed prevalence of thyroid disorder was 6.22%. Incidence of Subclinical hypothyroidism and clinical hypothyroidism was 3.77% and 2.45% respectively. In subclinical group and clinical group, they found, preeclampsia, preterm labour, first trimester miscarriage and Oligohydramnios in 13.75% versus 19.23%, 13.75% versus 36.54%, 11.25% versus 11.53%, and 16.25% versus 23.02% respectively. Subclinical hypothyroidism was more prevalent and hidden leading to the poor obstetrical outcome and fetal complications like low birth weight, prematurity and intrauterine growth restriction. There was higher incidence of caesarean deliveries in both groups more in clinical hypothyroid cases (49).

IMPACT OF SCH ON CONCEPTION AND MAINTENANCE OF PREGNANCY

Normal functioning of thyroid hormone is very necessary for normal conception and maintenance of pregnancy. Due to raised estradiol level during pregnancy, production of thyroid hormone increase by 50% in euthyroid women, functional reserve of thyroid is poor in hypothyroid women taking thyroxin, this phenomenon does not occur in hypothyroid women and they have to increase the dose of LT₄(29).

Overt and SCH both may result into ovulatory dysfunction, menstrual irregularities leading to Subfertility and miscarriages and the incidence of subfertility and miscarriage is reduced after treatment with LT₄ therapy (30) (33) (34) (35). All these risk are enhanced if the women is anti-thyroid antibody positive (36) (48). These effects are examined in most studies conducted in patients undergoing IVF cycles and most of them are retrospective studies. A study conducted in Beijing China showed hypothyroid patients with LT₄ treatment and TSH serum concentrations of 2.5-4.0 mIU/mL had significantly lower implantation and significantly higher pregnancy loss rates compared to euthyroid and unmedicated subclinical hypothyroid IVF patients. There is no evidence that IVF/ICSI outcomes were impaired among untreated subclinical hypothyroid patients compared with euthyroid patients (31) alternatively another study conducted in Canada showed an increase in incidence of miscarriage among women with SCH and reduced incidence of miscarriage in the group treated with LT₄ (32).

A study conducted in people's hospital of Yunnan Province PR China examined the rates of clinical pregnancy, miscarriage, and live birth in patients of SCH receiving LT₄ and euthyroid women undergoing IVF treatment. They found a similar rate of clinical pregnancy (47.4% vs 38.7%, $P = .436$), miscarriage (7.4% vs 16.7%, $P = .379$) and live birth (43.9% vs 32.3%, $P = .288$) between the two groups (29)

IMPACT OF SCH ON PREGNANCY AND NEONATAL OUTCOMES

Hypothyroidism during pregnancy is associated with adverse outcomes for both the mother and the fetus. Specifically, pregnant women with hypothyroidism have a greater risk of Experiencing obstetrical complications, including an increased risk of miscarriage, gestational Hypertension, low birth weight, fetal distress, and intrauterine fetal death furthermore, hypothyroidism has been correlated with a high risk of preterm birth and impairment of the child's neurologic development (50) (51).

Most of the current resources used to assess the prevalence and consequences of hypothyroidism during pregnancy were based on Western populations. However, thyroid function is dependent on nutritional iodine intake, environmental factors, diet, body habitus, and genetic predisposition, which can vary among different populations. Hence, it is warranted to estimate the prevalence and adverse effects of thyroid dysfunction in different populations_(41)

A prospective analytical study conducted in India found Incidence of SCH 9.5% and. Pregnant women with SCH had increased risks of developing anemia (31.5%), preeclampsia (15%), GDM (5%) and prematurity (10%), higher cesarean section rate (36.8%). Neonates of women with SCH had higher incidence poor APGAR score (47.36%), LBW (15%), NICU admission (10%), IUGR (5%) (38).

A study conducted in Japan showed that there is increased incidence of GDM in SCH, but there have been conflicting data concerning the impact of SCH on obstetrical outcomes. Elevated TSH was not associated with composite adverse maternal and neonatal outcome, without known medical complications. These results may be due to the fact that ,In Japani population, there is no iodine deficiency and SCH may be rather due to iodine exess and incidence of TPO anti-body also very low(42)

A study was conducted in Pakistan Naval Ship Shifa Hospital Karachi Pakistan, from Jun 2019 to May 2020 ,its results showed SCH women had significantly increased risk of gestational hypertension (RR= 4.795% CI=2.902 to 7.773, $p<0.0001$), preeclampsia (RR=4.07, 95%CI=2.315 to 7.197, $p<0.0001$), preterm delivery (RR= 4.1, 95% CI=2.128 to 7.89, $p<0.0001$), cesarean section rate (RR=2.3611, 95% CI=1.7106 to 3.2591, $p<0.0001$) and risk of IUGR (RR=8.000, 95% CI= 1.869 to 34.227, $p=0.005$) as compared to euthyroid women(2).

Study was conducted to see the fetomaternal outcome between preeclampsia patient with subclinical hypothyroidism and preeclampsia pt without hypothyroidism and found complications like abruption, intrauterine fetal death (IUD), intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), Oligohydramnios, preterm deliveries, postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), low birth weight babies, birth asphyxia in babies and subsequent neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admissions were significantly higher ($p <0.05$) in the preeclampsia patients with thyroid dysfunction SCH) in comparison with euthyroid ones(46).

Early diagnosis and management can cause effective prevention of adverse maternal and perinatal effects in pregnancy with subclinical hypothyroidism (23)

TREATMENT

Mathuriya et all compaired three groups overt hypothyroidism treated with SCH treated and SCH non treated gp.Presence of SCH in pregnancy can be expected to have adverse effects on the growth and development of the fetus. The adverse pregnancy outcomes include, miscarriage, pregnancy induced hypertension, and its more severe form pre-eclampsia, as well as placental abruption, anaemia, post-partum hemorrhage, and increased fetal morbidity and mortality. In this study they study the maternal and

perinatal outcome in mothers with subclinical hypothyroidism treated with thyroxine replacement therapy. Maternal anemia was most common finding in all the groups. Pregnant women with SCH had increased risks of GHTN and PROM, and their neonates had increased risks of IUGR and LBW. These adverse outcomes show a wide decreasing trend on levothyroxine administration in overt hypothyroidism but in SCH as our study reveals effects are limited. However, pregnancy loss widely decreased on levothyroxine administration as maternal outcome remain unaffected. Thyroid function test should be employed in all the pregnant women to detect and avoid the negative maternal and neonatal outcomes. Levothyroxine replacement therapy is safe and effective in case of subclinical and overt hypothyroidism & in SCH pregnancy loss in mother & neonatal admission rate to NICU shows a significant decrease on levothyroxine administration. (52)

Zhang et al observed in a retrospective observational study, conducted in china, whether SCH was well controlled by treatment (case Group-A: well controlled, n=55; case Group-B: poorly controlled, n=27, and clinical data from 41 healthy pregnant women from the same period as the control group. The incidence of premature rupture of membranes, neonatal respiratory distress premature delivery, abortion and neonatal growth restriction was higher in group B (53)

In pregnant women with SCH (TSH >2.5-6 mIU/L and Normal T4 level), treatment with Paul S Conversely Paul et al observed that thyroxin does not have any association in reducing the incidence of preterm labour Gestational Diabetes or Hypertension. Neonatal outcome was normal in both the groups. Overall maternal and neonatal outcome is comparable in both the groups. Benefits of treatment need to be weighed

against any potential risks. Over treatment of subclinical hypothyroidism can cause iatrogenic hyperthyroidism. (54)

A cross-sectional retrospective study conducted in downtown public university hospital CHU Saint-Pierre in Brussels, Belgium, examined the effect of levothyroxine therapy in subclinical hypothyroidism, they found that Pregnant women with untreated SCH and without TPOAb positivity had a higher prevalence of preeclampsia and GDM compared with euthyroid women, while this was not the case in women with treated SCH, even when it was initiated after the first trimester. Anemia was also less in treated group(55)

Further studies are needed to confirm the benefits of levothyroxine therapy in subclinical hypothyroidism during pregnancy, to bring it into routine clinical practice.

REFERENCES

1. Gupta S, Sinha S. Hypothyroidism in Mother and Child during Pregnancy and Its Effect on Fetomaternal Outcome. *Research Developments in Medicine and Medical Science* Vol 2. 2023:49-60.
2. Razzaq K, Anwar R, Noor N, Tariq A, Imran A, Iftikhar B, et al. Screening of Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Antenatal Women and its Impact on Pregnancy Outcomes. *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal*. 2022;72(SUPPL-2):S384-88.
3. Song W, Xu Y, Miao L, Guan H. Subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnant women with diabetes. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE*. 2020;13(3):1696-703.
4. Zhu P, Chu R, Pan S, Lai X, Ran J, Li X. Impact of TPOAb-negative maternal subclinical hypothyroidism in early pregnancy on adverse pregnancy outcomes. *Therapeutic Advances in Endocrinology and Metabolism*. 2021;12:20420188211054690.

5. Alexander EK, Pearce EN, Brent GA, Brown RS, Chen H, Dosiou C, et al. 2017 Guidelines of the American Thyroid Association for the diagnosis and management of thyroid disease during pregnancy and the postpartum. *Thyroid*. 2017;27(3):315-89.
6. Kaliannan C, Nalligounder P, Vijayan D, Muthiah K. A Study on the Effect of Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Pregnant Women with Bad Obstetric History. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2023;13(2).
7. Wu M-Q, Liu J, Wang Y-Q, Yang Y, Yan C-H, Hua J. The impact of subclinical hypothyroidism on adverse perinatal outcomes and the role of thyroid screening in pregnancy. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*. 2019;10:522.
8. Stagnaro-Green A, Abalovich M, Alexander E, Azizi F, Mestman J, Negro R, et al. Guidelines of the American Thyroid Association for the diagnosis and management of thyroid disease during pregnancy and postpartum. *Thyroid*. 2011;21(10):1081-125.
9. Siscart J, Orós M, Serna MC, Perejón D, Galván L, Ortega M. Adherence to treatment for hypothyroidism in pregnancy and relationship with thyrotropin control: a retrospective observational cohort study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*. 2022;22(1):168.
10. Dulek H, Vural F, Aka N, Zengin S. The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction and its relationship with perinatal outcomes in pregnant women in the third trimester. *North Clin Istanbul* 2019;6(3):267–272.
11. Khakurel G, Karki C, Chalise S. Prevalence of thyroid disorder in pregnant women visiting a tertiary care teaching hospital: a descriptive cross-sectional study. *JNMA: Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*. 2021;59(233):51.
12. Sharma S, Sharma D. Prevalence of thyroid disorders in pregnancy. *International Journal of Research & Review*. 2019;8:424-7.

13. Maraka S, Singh Ospina NM, Mastorakos G, O’Keeffe DT. Subclinical hypothyroidism in women planning conception and during pregnancy: who should be treated and how? *Journal of the Endocrine Society*. 2018;2(6):533-46.
14. Dhillon-Smith R, Coomarasamy A. TPO antibody positivity and adverse pregnancy outcomes. *Best practice & research Clinical endocrinology & metabolism*. 2020;34(4):101433.
15. Korevaar TI, Pop VJ, Chaker L, Goddijn M, De Rijke YB, Bisschop PH, et al. Dose dependency and a functional cutoff for TPO-antibody positivity during pregnancy. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2018;103(2):778-89.
16. Solha STG, Mattar R, Teixeira PdFdS, Chiamolera MI, Maganha CA, Zaconeta ACM, et al. Screening, diagnosis and management of hypothyroidism in pregnancy: Number 10–October 2022. *Revista Brasileira de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia*. 2022;44(10):999-1009.
17. guideline NG145 N. Thyroid disease: assessment and management.
18. Pop V, Broeren M, Wiersinga W, Stagnaro-Green A. Thyroid disease symptoms during early pregnancy do not identify women with thyroid hypofunction that should be treated. *Clinical endocrinology*. 2017;87(6):838-43.
19. Springer D, Jiskra J, Limanova Z, Zima T, Potlukova E. Thyroid in pregnancy: From physiology to screening. *Critical reviews in clinical laboratory sciences*. 2017;54(2):102-16.
20. Jain A, Ahirwar A, Dwivedi S, Rath RS. Prevalence and Complications of Subclinical and Overt Hypothyroidism in Pregnancy at North Indian Tertiary Care Center. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*. 2023;48(2):285-90.

21. Wagh RV, Mundra MR, Upadhye JJ, Telgote DB, Khillare SN, Ramteke PS. Thyroid screening in pregnancy. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2017;6(9):3956-9.
22. Li M, Ma L, Feng Q, Zhu Y, Yu T, Ke J, et al. Effects of maternal subclinical hypothyroidism in early pregnancy diagnosed by different criteria on adverse perinatal outcomes in Chinese women with negative TPOAb. *Front Endocrinol (lausanne)* 11: 580380. 2020.
23. Mahjabeen N, Tarafdar M. Study of Feto-Maternal Outcome in Pregnancy with Subclinical Hypothyroidism. *Womens Health Care*. (2023):2.
24. Sharmin F, Asma M, Tasnim KS, Momin A, Akhter S, Das TR, et al. Effect of Clinical and Subclinical Hypothyroidism on Fetal Outcomes among Pregnant Women: A Sub-Specialty Department Experience. *Journal of National Institute of Neurosciences Bangladesh*. 2021;7(1):29-32
25. Fathima Thasneem E, Shahnas M, Abdul Vahab K. Obstetric and neonatal outcome of thyroid dysfunction in pregnancy. 2019.
26. Kunwar R, Prajapati S, Jha A, Bhattarai A, Bogatee UB. Fetomaternal Outcome in Maternal Hypothyroidism Complicating Pregnancies at Paropakar Maternity and Women's Hospital. *Open Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2022;12(11):1121-8
27. Lalooei A, Beheshti F, Khalili N, Hashemi SR. The Prevalence and Fetal and Maternal Outcome of Overt and Subclinical Hypothyroidism among Pregnant Women; A Cross-sectional Study. *Canon Journal of Medicine*. 2023;4(1):18-21.
28. Dhillon-Smith RK, Boelaert K, Jevic YB, Maheshwari A, Coomarasamy A, Obstetricians RCo, et al. Subclinical hypothyroidism and antithyroid autoantibodies in women with

- subfertility or recurrent pregnancy loss: Scientific Impact Paper No. 70 June 2022. BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology. 2022;129(12):e75-e88.
29. Cai Y, Zhong L, Guan J, Guo R, Niu B, Ma Y, et al. Outcome of in vitro fertilization in women with subclinical hypothyroidism. *Reproductive Biology and Endocrinology*. 2017;15:1-6.
30. Feldt-Rasmussen U, Effraimidis G, Bliddal S, Klose M. Consequences of undertreatment of hypothyroidism. *Endocrine*. 2023:1-8.
31. Zhang L, Yang X, Sun X, Xu Y, Xue Q, Shang J, et al. Influence of hypothyroidism on in vitro fertilization outcomes. *Int J Clin Exp Med*. 2016;9(2):4551-6.
32. Grandi SM, Yu YH, Reynier P, Platt RW, Yu OH, Filion KB. Levothyroxine initiation and the risk of pregnancy loss among pregnant women with subclinical hypothyroidism: An observational study emulating a target trial. *Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology*. 2023.
33. Koyyada A, Orsu P. Role of hypothyroidism and associated pathways in pregnancy and infertility: Clinical insights. *Tzu chi medical journal*. 2020;32(4):312-7.
34. Priya DM, Akhtar N, Ahmad J. Prevalence of hypothyroidism in infertile women and evaluation of response of treatment for hypothyroidism on infertility. *Indian journal of endocrinology and metabolism*. 2015;19(4):504-6.
35. Chen Y-T, Ho C-H, Chung M-T, Wen J-Y, Lin Y-L, Hsiao T-W, et al. Effect of extra-low dose levothyroxine supplementation on pregnancy outcomes in women with subclinical hypothyroidism undergoing in vitro fertilization and embryo transfer. *Taiwanese Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2023;62(6):869-73

36. Kiran Z, Sheikh A, Islam N. Association of thyroid antibodies status on the outcomes of pregnant women with hypothyroidism (maternal hypothyroidism on pregnancy outcomes, MHPO-4). *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*. 2021;21:1-12..
37. Ezzeddine D, Ezzeddine D, Hamadi C, Abbas HA, Nassar A, Abiad M, et al. Prevalence and correlation of hypothyroidism with pregnancy outcomes among lebanese women. *Journal of the Endocrine society*. 2017;1(5):415-22.
38. Sannaboraiah A, Upadhyaya R, Garag S, Krishnappa S. Subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy and outcomes. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2017;6(4):1215-21.
39. Sohail R, Yasmin H, Tasneem N, Khanum Z, Sachdev PS, Pal SA, et al. The Prevalence of Subclinical Hypothyroidism During Early Pregnancy in Pakistan: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus*. 2021;13(12).
40. Al Shanqeeti SA, Alkhudairy YN, Alabdulwahed AA, Ahmed AE, Al-Adham MS, Mahmood NM. Prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Medical Journal*. 2018;39(3):254.
41. Ezzeddine D, Ezzeddine D, Hamadi C, Abbas HA, Nassar A, Abiad M, et al. Prevalence and correlation of hypothyroidism with pregnancy outcomes among lebanese women. *Journal of the Endocrine society*. 2017;1(5):415-22.
42. Furukawa S, Miyakawa K, Shibata J, Iwashita M. Women with subclinical hypothyroidism are at low risk of poor pregnancy outcome in Japan. *The Tohoku journal of experimental medicine*. 2017;242(3):167-72.
43. Sharmeen M, Shamsunnahar P, Laita T, Chowdhury S. Overt and subclinical hypothyroidism among Bangladeshi pregnant women and its effect on fetomaternal outcome. *Bangladesh Med Res Counc Bull*. 2014;40(2):52-7.

44. Kumari A, Srivastav R, Mitra S. Prevalence of thyroid dysfunction and its effects on fetomaternal outcome in pregnant women of eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2018;7(11):4379-83.
45. Joshi K, Bhatt M, Saxena R. Incidence of thyroid dysfunction in antenatal women and its effect on fetomaternal outcome. *International Archives of Integrated Medicine*. 2016;3(11).
46. Banik P, Devi R, Bidya A, Tamphasana A, Agalya M, Singh LR. Thyroid dysfunction in preeclampsia and related fetomaternal outcomes. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2019;8(5):1928-33.
47. Chen L-M, Du W-J, Dai J, Zhang Q, Si G-X, Yang H, et al. Effects of subclinical hypothyroidism on maternal and perinatal outcomes during pregnancy: a single-center cohort study of a Chinese population. *PloS one*. 2014;9(10):e109364.
48. Rajoriya M, Singh D. The analysis of pregnancy with hypothyroidism and fetomaternal outcome in MGM medical college, Indore.
49. Gupta M, Pandotra P, Jindal M, Jamwal G, Goraya S, Gupta V. Comparative study of fetomaternal outcome in clinical and subclinical hypothyroidism. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2017;6(5):1909-14.
50. Singh G, Kaul I, Singh A, Meinia SK. Maternal and fetal outcome in subclinical hypothyroidism in Jammu region, North India. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2016;5(7):2362-7.
51. Wang X, Zhang E, Tian Z, Zhao R, Huang K, Gao S, et al. The association between dyslipidaemia in the first trimester and adverse pregnancy outcomes in pregnant

- women with subclinical hypothyroidism: a cohort study. *Lipids in Health and Disease*. 2024;23(1):13.
52. Mathuriya G, Panday S. Levothyroxine replacement in subclinical hypothyroidism during pregnancy and its effect on fetomaternal outcome.
53. Zhang J, Chen H, Dou X, Huang W, Zeng H. Association between gestational blood lipids and TSH levels and pregnancy outcome of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2023;39(3):721.
54. Paul S, Nayak M. Pregnancy outcome in women treated for subclinical hypothyroidism detected in early gestation. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2018;7(2):685-9.
55. Sitoris G, Veltri F, Jelloul E, Kleynen P, Rozenberg S, Poppe KG. Impact of thyroid hormone treatment on maternal pregnancy outcomes in women with subclinical hypothyroidism without TPOAb: a retrospective cross-sectional study. *Thyroid Research*. 2023;16(1):29